

Due to the fact that the questions contained a varying number of response options, appropriate conversion factors and formulas had to be applied to ensure that each question was equally significant and carried the same weight. The standard was established for questions with three response options, where the multiplier was set to x1. For questions with four response options, the multiplier was x0.5, and for those with five options, it was x0.3. The scoring was assigned based on the number of available responses, with the highest number of points awarded to the most environmentally sustainable decision, gradually decreasing by one point until the least sustainable decision, which received no points. For three-option questions, the highest possible score was 2, followed by 1 for the middle option, while the last option received 0 points. In the case of four-option questions, the highest-scoring response could receive 3 points, followed by 2, then 1, and finally 0. For five-option questions, the maximum possible score was 4, followed by 3, then 2, then 1, and finally 0.

For example, a score of 2 points in a three-option question is equivalent to 3 points in a four-option question because the maximum point values in each scale represent the same level of response intensity, regardless of the number of available choices. In a three-option question, the point scale is 0, 1, 2, while in a four-option question, it is 0, 1, 2, 3. However, applying the 0.5 multiplier adjusts the point distribution to maintain proportionality in the impact of responses on the final score. Ultimately, the highest values in each scale correspond to the same level of response intensity, ensuring consistency and comparability of evaluations across the entire questionnaire. This approach eliminates the risk that questions with a greater number of response options would disproportionately influence the final result. Summing up using the multipliers, the total score for different response options always amounts to 3 each time.

Formula examples for Excel:

- Questions with three possible responses
`=IF(D3=A31;"0";IF(D3=A32;"1";IF(D3=A33;"2")))`
- Questions with four possible responses
`„=IF(B3=A31;"0";IF(B3=A32;"1";IF(B3=A33;"3";IF(B3=A34;"2"))))*0,5"`
- Questions with five possible responses
`„=IF(N5=A31;"4";IF(N5=A32;"3";IF(N5=A33;"2";IF(N5=A34;"1";IF(N5=A35;"0"))))*0,3"`